

Toxicological study with induced stress response in freshwater fish, *Puntius sophore* from Shivan River, Nandurbar, Maharashtra

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Abstract

Nano-fertilizers represent a new frontier in a sustainable agriculture with IFFCO Nano urea plus 16% nitrogen (w/v) emerging as a pioneering product since its launch in 2021. Designed to enhance nutrient use efficiency and reduce environmental burden, it has been widely praised for its eco-friendly profile however currently restricted to plant-based studies. Aquatic ecosystems open receive runoff from agriculture fields, making it imperative to investigate the Eco toxicological effects of Nano-fertilizers on non-target organisms. This study able to find out the general vulnerability of fish to high concentrations of nitrogenous compounds and nanoparticles in their habitat. This study suggests that the release of nano urea into water bodies, especially at high concentrations, could pose a risk to *Puntius sophore* and other aquatic life.

Keywords: Toxicological study, *Puntius sophore*, Shivan River, Nandurbar.

1. Introduction:

Puntius sophore (pool barb), a freshwater fish species, is commonly found in the Shivan River near Nandurbar, Maharashtra. Researchers have utilized samples of this species from this location to study the toxicological impacts of insecticides like cypermethrin on fish, as well as the protective, anti-stress role of ascorbic acid (Vitamin C) on their physiology and metabolism (B.R. Shinde 2018; B. R. Shinde et al., 2019). Nano urea, an innovative agricultural input based on nanotechnology, offers a particle size of 20 to 50 nm, providing a significantly larger surface area compared to conventional urea prills (Raliya et al., 2017; Mahapatra et al., 2022). The Indian Farmers Fertilizer Cooperative (IFFCO) nano urea (liquid) is officially recognized by the Government of India under the Fertilizer (Inorganic, Organic or Mixed) Order 1985. With a particle size of less than 100 nm, it contains 4% nitrogen (N) and has a shelf-life of approximately 2 years (Madhavi et al., 2022). The liquid nano urea, with a zeta

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potential greater than 30 for stability, is applied by spraying at a rate of 2-4 ml per liter of water, depending on crop nitrogen requirements, canopy development, and water needs (Lakshman et al., 2022).

Nano-fertilizers represent a new Frontier in a sustainable agriculture with IFFCO Nano urea plus 16% nitrogen (w/v) emerging as a pioneering product since its launch in 2021(Kumar et al., 2021). Designed to enhance nutrient use efficiency and reduce environmental burden, it has been widely praised for its eco-friendly profile however currently restricted to plant-based studies. While its benefits to crops are well documented, there remains critical gap in understanding its potential toxicity to aquatic life.

Agricultural runoff primarily includes water that flows over cultivated fields, carrying with it pesticides, fertilizers, animal waste, and soil particles into nearby rivers, lakes, and oceans. This runoff doesn't just dilute into the water it transforms the aquatic environment. Once in the water, pesticides can bioaccumulate in fish tissues, altering their physiology, behavior, and reproductive success (Shrivastava et al., 2025). Aquatic ecosystems open receive runoff from agriculture fields, making it imperative to investigate the ecotoxicological effects of Nano-fertilizers on non-target organisms. While nano urea is designed to be more efficient for plant uptake and reduce environmental losses, its impact on, *Puntius sophore* has not been explicitly studied.

Fig.1. Location map of Shivan River

Fig.2. *Puntius sophore*

2. Study Area:

The Shivan River near Nandurbar is a source for collecting healthy, medium-sized *Puntius sophore* for research (S. S. Patole 2014). The Shivan River is a 59.33 km long river in the Nandurbar district of Maharashtra, acting as a crucial left-bank tributary to the Tapi River. It originates in the

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northern Sahyadri ranges (706 m elevation) and flows through a 262 km² basin characterized by volcanic dykes. The river, with the Virchek project on it, serves as a vital water source for Nandurbar city. The Shivan River basin area extends from 21°10'49.3"N to 21°30'51.3"N latitudes and 74°05'23.0"E to 74°16'15.3"E longitudes (Fig. 1) (Bhise et al., 2024).

3. Materials and Methods:

Medium sized freshwater fishes, *Puntius sophore* were collected from Shiven River area Nandurbar Dist. Nandurbar. They were transferred to the glass aquarium and acclimatized to the laboratory conditions in the department of Zoology for two weeks and inspected for any possible injury or infection. Injured fishes were avoided. Only healthy fishes of different weight with length group of 10 mm range were selected. The physico-chemical parameters of the water used by the methods APHA and AWWA, 2005 (APHA 2005). Fishes were washed with 0.1% of potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) solution to avoid dermal infection. They were then rinsed in water. Dead fish were removed immediately that such mortality may deplete dissolved oxygen with resultant effect on other fishes. During acclimatization fishes were fed with pieces of live earthworm on alternate days. Water also changed once in every day. The experiment was conducted natural and photoperiod of temperature 27.1 ± 3.2 °C, Conductivity- 0.65 ± 0.3 , Dissolved O₂- 6.4 ± 1.1 (ml/L), pH- 8.65 ± 0.3 , Acidity- 2.7 ± 0.1 , Alkalinity- 45.1 ± 0.5 , Total hardness- 67.6 ± 0.3 .

Test groups: The fishes were divided into five groups A, B, C, D and E.

Group A fishes were maintained as a control 0ml/l (n =10). The group B fishes were exposed to 3ml/l (n =10) dose of Nano Urea plus, group C fishes were exposed to 6ml/L (n =10) dose of Nano Urea plus, group D fishes were exposed to 9ml/l (n =10) dose of Nano Urea plus, while group E fishes were exposed to 12ml/l (n =10) dose of Nano Urea plus and they are monitored for 96 hrs.

4. Result and Discussion

Following toxicological induced stress behaviour changes has been observed during experiment after being exposed to Nano urea a. fishes shows grouping under stress b. excessive mucus secretion c. surface gulping d. lesion over body e. froth formation under aeration increased opercular rate.

➤ No mortality was observed until is 72 hours there after sharp increases occurred at 3 and 6 ml/l.

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- Higher concentration (9 and 12 ml/l) showed no mortality throughout the test period.
- A dose-dependent increase in all behavioural stress indicators was observed, with the highest scores recorded at 12 ml/l indicating significant physiological stress under higher exposure levels.
- Aeration significantly influenced mortality, enhancing foam and possible Ammonia toxicity.
- Early deaths in the 3 ml/l tank (with aeration) and sudden death post-aeration in 6 ml/L suggest aeration induced stress.
- Motility may not solely be due to concentration but due to synergistic effect of aeration and Nano urea exposure.

Fig 3. Behavioural stress response in *Puntius sophore* exposed to diff. concen of Nano Urea for 96 hrs.

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